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Pragma-Rhetoric Analysis of Political Speeches on Islamophobia by Muslim Leaders at the United Nations (2012-2021)

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Abstract: *Muslim countries have been dealing with Islamophobia mainly after 9/11, facing vitriolic and marginalized attitudes from the world. This crisis has stemmed hatred and radicalization toward Muslims. The research aims to investigate how Muslim leaders, in their UN speeches, presented the image of Islam by combating Islamophobia. The corpus of Muslim leaders' UN speeches (2012-2021) serves as the data for the current research. The goal was to examine the pragmatic and rhetorical aspects in the speeches of Muslim leaders regarding Islamophobia. The data was analyzed in three steps: (1) concordance analysis using AntConc (3.5.7) software, (2) eclectic approach (qualitative analysis) based on Searle's (1969) speech act theory and Grundy's (2013) rhetorical appeals, and (3) quantitative analysis. The quantitative mode scrutinized rhetorical devices and speech acts employed, while the qualitative mode analyzed statistical data to derive answers for the research questions. The findings reveal that among all Muslim countries' UN speeches considered, Pakistan remains at the top while addressing the delicate issue of Islamophobia (26,791 total words, 18 uses of "Islamophobia"). Pakistan predominantly used representative speech acts (41.667%), logos rhetorical appeals (66.667%), and overstatements (88.235%). Turkey followed with 30,536 words and 12 uses of "Islamophobia," while Afghanistan had 17,713 words with 2 uses of "Islamophobia. Muslim leaders effectively employ pragma-rhetorical strategies to counter Islamophobia and present a positive image of Islam. For future researchers, a comparative study of Muslim countries and Western countries regarding Islamophobia can be conducted.*

Keywords: Islamophobia, Islam, Pragma-Rhetorical analysis, Pakistan, Muslim leaders, UN, Speech Acts, Rhetorical appeals

1. INTRODUCTION

The term Islamophobia, derived from "Islam" and "Phobos" (Greek for "fear"), means fear of Islam, "prejudice against Muslims, or depiction of Islam as a religion of radicals" (Ergül, 2017, p. 01). Islamophobic dread and hatred results in fear and dislike of Muslims. The West's irrational anti-Islam rhetoric depicts Islam as a religion of the savage and uneducated to alienate people from Islam with the narrative that Islam teaches terrorism, violence and violation of fundamental human rights.

Islamophobia aims to stop the expansion of Islam by instilling fear in people's minds. To promote harmony and peace, the West must restrict Islamophobic conduct (Arshad et al., 2021). Post-9/11, Islamophobia rose in EU countries (Allen, 2004). Many articles, movies, and photographs were published against Muslims, posing severe problems for Muslim countries.

Islamophobia is an ancient dread that gets a new name and is based on religious intolerance (Iqbal, 2010), which confuses Islam and Muslims into a single entity, leading to an increased focus on anti-Islamic propaganda (Abbas, 2019). This prevailing radicalization of Muslims based on their traits (physical and cultural), social activities, attire, and language stems from a racial logic (Carr & Haynes,

2015), obscuring Muslim heterogeneity and diversity, echoing the claim of various scholars (see Rana, 2007, & Bayrakli, 2016) that Muslims are reduced to a single, unchangeable, and fixed group, with their multiplicity disregarded.

Cervi (2020) distinguishes between "banal Islamophobia" and "ontological Islamophobia." He constructs a model that explains how prejudice against Muslims and Islam is not only predicated but also reifies emotional distance from Muslims. "Banal Islamophobia," according to Cervi (2020), fosters the "othering process," which is predicated on the Muslims' appearance (physical qualities and social activities), posing a threat to dominant groups' cultural and traditional lives. Whereas, ontological Islamophobia is a fear of Islam that is based on the belief that Islam's fundamental principles and Islamic civilization are opposed to the West and its core values.

Overall, definitions of Islamophobia tend to be polarizing, concentrating on racism and religious prejudice. Hence, one cannot deny that Islamophobia is based on opposition and differences that increase societal schisms.

Islamophobic narratives based on binaries, oppositions, and "Us" against "Them" schema, should be addressed by counter-narratives opposing Islamophobia. Therefore, this research aimed to evaluate the speech of famous Muslim leaders who actively combat Islamophobia on a global scale. Keeping in view the preliminaries stated above, this study explored the role of Muslim leaders' UN speeches in diminishing the negative image of Islam and Muslims in the aftermath of 9/11. A corpus-based approach to pragma-rhetorical analysis is used for data analysis, employing several strategies, such as the eclectic model developed by Searle (1969) and Grundy (2013).

Al-Kawwaz and Al-Tamimi (2020) defines pragma-rhetorical perspective as "the term 'pragma-rhetorical' simply describes the use of pragmatic and rhetorical devices and strategies in analyzing certain stretches of speech" (p. 413).

The primary purpose of pragma-rhetoric is to connect rhetoric with pragmatics while combining communicative and persuasive intent. These two aims are clearly at opposite ends of the spectrum. The accomplishment of communicative purpose comes first, followed by persuasive intention. The goal of persuasion is the common thread that connects rhetoric and argument. The current research has used Larrazabal and Korta's (2002) pragma-rhetorical notion, in which pragmatic and rhetorical devices and strategies are discovered and analyzed separately.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The negative image of Islam and Muslims has been rapidly increasing in the world since 9/11. Some Muslim leaders tried to portray the actual image of Islam in the annual meetings of UNGA by highlighting the issue of Islamophobia to build a positive image of Islam in their speeches; whereas other Muslim leaders paid little attention to addressing this issue in the last decade. This research analyzed how all the Muslim leaders portray the image of Islam in their UN speeches (2012-2021).

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The study has following objectives:

- I. To investigate the speech acts projecting Islamophobia used by the Muslim leaders at the UN (2012-2021).
- II. To analyze rhetorical devices, including ethos, logos and pathos used in the speeches of Muslim leaders at the UN (2012-2021).
- III. To examine the other figure of speeches such as metaphors, overstatements and understatements used in the speeches of Muslim leaders at the UN (2012-2021).

1.3 Research Questions

This research answers following questions:

- I. What kind of speech acts are used by the Muslim leaders at the UN (2012-2021) to project Islamophobia?
- II. How are rhetorical devices such as ethos, logos and pathos used in Muslim leaders' UN speeches (2012-2021)?
- III. How other figures of speeches such as metaphors, overstatements and understatements used in the speeches of Muslim leaders at the UN (2012-2021)?

1.4 Significance of the Research

By analyzing Muslim leaders' speeches at UN, this study reveals the stance taken by Muslim leaders through their linguistic choices. The results give insight on how the political leaders eliminate a negative image of Islam while helping us understand techniques deployed by the Muslim leaders to counter Islamophobia. This thesis would help rhetoricians, pragmatists, and psycholinguists interested in countering Islamophobia by persuading people through the use of language.

1.5 Limitations of the Study

This thesis analyzes the UN speeches of Pakistani, Turkish and Afghan Muslim leaders from 2012-2021 to find the rhetorical and pragmatic devices used to counter Islamophobia. This research's corpus includes speeches of Muslim Prime Ministers, Presidents and Foreign Ministers. The speeches chosen for analysis are downloaded from UN's official website. UN is an international organization that deals with global concerns and has as its primary goal the maintenance of peace and security, and collaboration and cordial ties between nations. AntConc (3.5.7) software is used for corpus study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Islamophobia

Following the attacks of 11 September 2001, evidence of the rise of Islamophobia was collected by Gallup, Inc and the Council on American-Islamic Relations (CAIR). Gallup's Center for Islamic Studies reports that 43 per cent of Americans have some degree of prejudice against Muslims. The Gallup publication *Religious Perceptions in America: With an in-depth analysis of U.S. attitudes towards Muslims and Islam* (2009) reports that Islam was perceived worse than any other religious faith (Christianity, Judaism, Buddhism, and Islam), with 53 per cent expressing an 'opinion of Islam [as] not too favourable', which was twice as high as any of the other religious groups studied.

In 2015, CAIR fielded 1,556 complaints from Muslims alleging religious discrimination in the workplace, police and FBI abuses, hate crimes, discrimination at higher education institutions, housing discrimination, school bullying, and travel discrimination (CAIR, 2016). CAIR issues an annual report on the status of Muslim civil rights in the US. In 2014, CAIR received 1,136 complaints about civil rights violations, an increase of 35 per cent over what it recorded the following year.

The media frequently reinforces Muslims' societal "othering" by characterizing them as "enemies" or "extremists" (Saeed, 2007). This can be particularly troublesome because many people base their viewpoints and attitudes entirely on information that is frequently misrepresented in the media.

Post-9/11, Arabs and Muslims were dehumanized in the Western media (Steuter & Wills, 2010). Metaphors such as animal, vermin, and metastatic cancer were utilized for Muslims. Edward Said (1981), in his book *Orientalism*, claims that the West views Islam as dogmatic and unfit for current Western philosophy and multiculturalism, while the Arab is frequently depicted in Western discourse

as a savage Oriental.

Islamophobia is not a new phenomenon, and the modern era's hatred of Muslims is not limited to language. Today, there is a widespread belief among Muslims worldwide that the Western world contains a great deal of negative stereotyping (Said, 1997).

Sultan (2016) highlighted the media's role as a manipulator and how Islam was associated with terrorism in Western media, while Muslims were portrayed as terrorists. Several researchers have looked into its existence prior to 9/11 (Allen & Nielsen, 2002).

Some Muslim leaders, including Imran Khan, Pakistan's Ex-Prime Minister, spoke out against the phenomenon that has caused so much misery and suffering for Muslims and Islam at the UNGA. Khan's and other Muslim leaders' speeches attempted to offer his side of the story to demonstrate that there is no such thing as radical Islam, debunking the notion that Islam is a violent religion instead of blaming the West for causing a divide between itself and the Muslims. This research aims to analyze Muslim leaders' language to comment on the critical status of Muslims around the world, and to show how Islamophobia is a Western invention. In this regard, this research will examine methods used by Muslim leaders to condemn Western anti-Islam discourse.

2.2 Pragmatics

Pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that scrutinizes the role of context in the formation of meaning. Pragmatics "is concerned with meaning in the context of language use" (Mey, 2009, p. 744). It is an attempt to solve problems regarding meaning, specifically the relationship between what sentences signify and what speakers mean by them (Allott, 2010, p.14). Pragmatics also studies how the context affects meaning (Yule, 1996, p.3-4).

The pragmatic analysis of language looks at that component which means that it is no longer acquired from the formal qualities of phrases and structures. Adebija (1999) elaborates on the scope of pragmatics that includes: the message being communicated, the individuals concerned in the message, the information of the world which they proportion, the deductions to be crafted from the text on the premise of the context and the impact of the non-verbal aspect of the interaction of that means.

2.3 Rhetoric

Rhetoric, which dates back to Aristotle, Socrates, and Plato, is one of the oldest branches of knowledge. According to Kennedy (2007), rhetoric is the energy contained in emotion and thinking that is communicated to others through a system of signs, including language, to influence their decisions or actions. Rhetoric occurs when we express our feelings and thoughts to others to influence (persuade) them.

Rhetoric has gone through numerous stages of development, with the fundamental goal of demonstrating the varied modes of persuasion. In this regard, Roberts (2004) delineates rhetoric as "the faculty of observing in any given case the available means of persuasion" (p. 07). Three aspects of rhetoric are: "logos, ethos, and pathos."

2.4 Pragma-Rhetoric Perspective

For discourse analysis, pragma-rhetoric provides a unique interdisciplinary theoretical and methodological framework. The collaboration between the two disciplines (pragmatics and rhetoric) is justified not only by their shared research topic, which is language in use but also by the similarity of their approaches to this object, which is the speaker's aim to generate a specific effect on the receiver. As it focuses on a goal-oriented speech situation, Leech (1983) was the first to characterize the pragmatics method as "rhetorical".

The union of rhetoric and pragmatics is a union of the 'ancient' and the 'modern'. The fundamental

reason for such a union is that the two are concerned with how language is used. Rhetoric is already pragmatic because it deals with something other than what is directly articulated (Persson & Ylikoski, 2007, p. 55).

Rhetoric, like pragmatics, tries to influence reality through the use of linguistic devices. Larsson (1998) distinguished rhetoric following persuasion and pragmatics following description.

2.5 An Eclectic Model for Pragma-Rhetoric Analysis

An eclectic model based on "Searle's (1969) speech acts and Grundy's (2008) rhetorical appeals" has been used for this research to achieve the aim of the research (i.e., pragma-rhetorical analysis of all the Muslim countries' UN speeches). This eclectic model consists of two major components: the pragmatic strategies (including speech acts) and rhetorical strategies such as (ethos, logos, pathos and figures of speech).

Figure 1: Eclectic Model for Analysis

2.5.1 Pragmatic Strategies

Pragmatic strategies include speech acts. To comprehend speech acts, the context is important. An utterance cannot be understood without a suitable context; speech act theory cannot be understood without pragmatics. Al-Kawwaz and Al-Tamimi (2020) elucidate that speech acts "as an act, persuasion is an effort on the part of an addresser to change the opinion, attitude, or belief of an addressee" (p. 413).

The speech act theory was introduced by Austin (1962) and further developed by Searle (1969) which

considers utterances at three levels or parts: locutionary acts, illocutionary acts and perlocutionary acts. Locutionary acts are making meaningful statements or saying something the listener can comprehend. Illocutionary acts include something said with a purpose or aim to inform the listener. It is also regarded as the "real action" that is performed via utterances. Its effect on the listeners is called the perlocutionary effect.

Searle has divided the illocutionary acts into five different classes:

Representatives: Committed to what the speaker thinks or feels the case to be – they express their capabilities. Uses verbs like report, conclude, deny, believe, and indicate (or affirm) (Searle, 1969).

Expressives: Tells one about speaker's attitude and psychological acts by using verbs like regret, welcome, thank you, apologies, detest, appreciate, deplore etc.

Directives: Speaker demands someone else to do something. Uses words like invite, request, command, beg and challenge.

Commissives: Requires speakers to commit themselves to some future actions. Uses verbs like pledge, swear, warrant, and vow.

Declaratives: Can change the whole aura of utterances. Speaker has the liberty to change the condition of the situation by uttering words.

2.5.2 Rhetorical Strategies

2.5.2.1 Logos: Aristotle defined logos as logical, reasonable, and argumentative discourse. Logos refers to reasoning-based persuasion; to put it another way, it refers to applying logic to arguments. As a result, to verify logical discussion, one must appeal to reason. Reasoning ensures that the claim is clear, that the rationale is logical, and that the confirming proof is effective (Walton, 2007, p. 18).

2.5.2.2 Ethos: Ethos is concerned with speaker's or writer's trustworthiness (or credibility) (O'Shaughnessy, 2004, p. 145). As a result, they are characteristics of speaker to carry out an argument. It strongly links to the audience's perception of how "believable" a speaker is. This persuasive appeal's effectiveness stems from its emphasis on what is just, good, and fair (Betty et al., 2006, p. 232).

2.5.2.3 Pathos: The term 'pathos' refers to emotional appeals that aim to make the addressees feel furious, empathetic, fearful, disagreeable, egotistical, subservient, and humiliated, among other emotions. As a result, the appeal to pathos aims to arouse the audience's emotions. In many instances, particularly in political discussions, emotion is the most important and convincing aspect.

2.5.2.4 Figures of Speech: Rhetorical figurative speech is one of the various ways to display a message in a particular setting. The three figures of speech used in this research are:

Metaphor: Talking about something in terms of something else that overlaps with it in certain areas.

Overstatement: A rhetorical strategy in which "the speaker's description is stronger than the state of circumstances represented" (Leech, 1983, p. 145).

Understatement: Refers to a kind of expression that involves seriousness, quantity and intensity of what is less than the reality to generate an impact on the addressee (Cruse, 2006, p. 186).

2.6 Corpus Linguistics

Corpus linguistics (CL) is a "methodological basis for doing linguistic research" (Leech, 1992, p. 105). Biber et al. (1998) define four characteristics of corpus-based research:

- Empirical: investigates fundamental patterns of use in natural texts.
- Analyzes an extensive collection of natural texts called corpus.
- Employs both quantitative and qualitative methods of analysis.

- Uses computers for analysis, employing both automatic and interactive techniques.

According to Hunston (2002), "it is no exaggeration to claim that corpora and the study of corpora have changed the study of language, and its applications, during the previous few decades" (p. 1).

2.7 Previous Researches

Akinwotu (2016) illustrates the communicative intentions and persuasive techniques employed in selected political speeches of Obafemi Awolowo and Moshood Abiola, two famous political figures in the history of Nigerian Politics. The author examined the deployment of rhetoric used by Nigerian politicians during different times in Nigeria's history. The findings suggest that the selected speeches are highly persuasive in their approach as they employed two types of rhetoric: combat and tact.

Abdel-Moety (2015) analyzed President El-Sisi's first inaugural address by interpreting it through rhetorical and linguistic methods.

2.8 Research Gap

Most previous research on Islamophobia focused on various language aspects, including lexicalization and ideology in texts and speeches. Moreover, in the reviewed literature, Islamophobia has been addressed from different angles, yet its pragmatic and rhetorical aspect has not been given much attention. This study intends to fill the gap by analyzing the Muslim leaders' speeches using the pragma-rhetorical approach to find the image of Islam presented at UN (2012-2021).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

For in-depth understanding, a mixed-method technique was used, which incorporates the aspects of quantitative and qualitative methods. The qualitative part sought an in-depth discussion of the data to discover the pragma-rhetorical elements of the speeches of the Muslim leaders at the UN. The quantitative part of the study was devoted to examining the statistical findings of the study. According to Duff (2010) "quantitative and qualitative approaches are currently viewed as complementary rather than fundamentally incompatible, and a more mixed-paradigm research is recommended" (p. 54).

3.2 Data Collection

3.2.1 The Corpus Description

For this research, Pakistani, Turkish and Afghan Muslim leaders' speeches at the annual meeting of the United National General Assembly (UNGA) from 2012 to 2021 were examined. A specialized corpus was compiled specifically to cover a time span of 10 years. Transcripts were downloaded from UN's official website. Afterwards, the researcher converted the PDF format speeches into "txt. form" with notepad text editor. Analysis was conducted country-wise from the countries addressing Islamophobia, ranging from maximum to minimum. This research uploaded UN speeches of 3 Muslim countries on AntConc (3.5.7) software.

Table 1: Frequency of Words Used by Three Muslim Countries' Leaders in their UN Speeches (2012-2021)

Sr. No.	Countries	Frequencies
1	Afghanistan	17,713
2	Pakistan	26,791

Sr. No.	Countries	Frequencies
3	Turkey	30,536

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

The researcher searched the term "Islamophobia" in the search box to find sentences with the term Islamophobia from the corpus of speeches. This data was analyzed in three steps: firstly, concordance analysis using AntConc software; secondly, qualitative analysis of sentences in the light of Searle's (1969) and Grundy's (2013) eclectic model; thirdly, quantitative analysis to examine the relative frequencies of speech acts, rhetorical appeals and other figures of speech.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Concordance Analysis

For concordance analysis, the themes were extracted by searching terminologies like "Islamophobia, peace-loving religion, Islam, moderate, tolerance, compassion, rational, terrorism, terrorist, radicals, extremists, intolerant, hatred, prejudice, fear, Islamic terrorism and radical Islam" in the search box.

Table 2: Frequencies of Keywords Used by Muslim Countries while Addressing Islamophobia

Keywords	Pakistan	Turkey	Afghanistan
Islamophobia	18	12	2
Islam	25	11	7
Radical Islam	6	-	-
Religion	17	8	4
Minorities	8	7	1
Compassion	3	-	1
Tolerance	1	2	3
Love	1	1	1
Prophet	16	1	-
Medina	3	-	-
Muslims	-	17	1
Discrimination	3	6	1
Racism	2	10	-
Violence	17	9	13
Radicalization	3	1	-
Terrorism	73	30	49
Terror	8	4	7
Terrorist	18	64	21
Terrorists	22	14	9

Keywords	Pakistan	Turkey	Afghanistan
Extremism	8	3	8
Extremists	7	1	2
Extremist	2	1	2
Prejudice	-	4	-
Islamic terrorism	6	-	-
Fear	3	2	-
Hatred	7	5	4
Total	279	213	146

4.2 Pakistan

Table 3: Representation of Islamophobia by Pakistan

Sr. No.	Sentences	Speaker	Year
1	This assembly should declare an "International Day to Combat Islamophobia" and build a resilient coalition to fight this scourge - scourge that splits humanity.	Imran Khan	2020
2	The terms "Islamic terrorism" and "Islamic radicalism", which are used by leaders, sadly, are the main reasons for Islamophobia and have caused pain against Muslims.	Imran Khan	2019
3	What message do the terms "radical Islam" and "Islamic terrorism" send to people in the West, and why does Islamophobia exist?	Imran Khan	2019
4	Since 9/11, Islamophobia has grown at an alarming pace.	Imran Khan	2019
5	Islamophobia is another pernicious phenomenon that we all need to collectively combat.	Imran Khan	2021
6	Human communities live together and should foster understanding among one another, but Islamophobia is creating a division.	Imran Khan	2019
7	Rising racism and religious hatred, manifested in xenophobia and Islamophobia, is erecting physical walls and psychological barriers, among nations and people.	Shahid Khaqan Abbasi	2017
8	The one country in the world today where the state sponsors Islamophobia is India.	Imran Khan	2020
9	I also say that Islamophobia is marginalizing the Muslim communities in European countries, and we all know that marginalization leads to radicalization.	Imran Khan	2019
10	The most important thing I want to say here today with regard to Islamophobia is this; I know how the misunderstanding about Islam came about, because I have spent a lot of time in England playing	Imran Khan	2019

Sr. No.	Sentences	Speaker	Year
	sport professionally.		
11	These trends have also accentuated 'Islamophobia'; Muslims continue to be targeted with impunity in many countries. Our shrines are being destroyed; our Prophet insulted; the Holy Quran burnt — and all this in the name of freedom of speech.	Imran Khan	2020
12	The worst and most pervasive form of Islamophobia now rules in India.	Imran Khan	2021
13	We hope the Secretary-General's report will focus on these new threats of terrorism posed by Islamophobes and right-wing extremist.	Imran Khan	2021
14	In many countries, intolerance has revived the ghosts of xenophobia and Islamophobia.	Nawaz Sharif	2016
<u>15</u>	I therefore know how the Western mind works and how the West views religion, one of the reasons for Islamophobia was a book published in 1989 that maligned, insulted and ridiculed our Prophet Muhammad.	Imran Khan	2019
<u>16</u>	We experience Islamophobia when travelling abroad, and it is getting worse.	Imran Khan	2019
<u>17</u>	The reason is Islamophobia, which started after 9/11, because certain Western leaders equated terrorism with Islam, talking of Islamic terrorism and radical Islam.	Imran Khan	2019

2 is therefore going against the religion of Islam and our Prophet. It is important to
3 either. After 9/11, when the war against radical Islam began, leaders did not try to explain
4 — and Muslims would react, which led to Islam being labelled an intolerant religion. In more
5 Muslims will become radicalized — not because of Islam, but because they will see that there
6 rist attacks, terrorism has been associated with Islam by some quarters. This has increased the
7 this. I know how the misunderstanding about Islam came about, because I have spent a
8 State? I hear such strange things about Islam — for example, that it is against women
9 women and minorities. The first State of Islam, in Medina, was the first welfare State.
10 on that account is unfair and unwise. Islam is a religion of peace, compassion and
11 in India. The Assembly has heard that Islam is supposedly against minorities, so let me
12 are Christian, Jewish or anything else — but Islam itself is not radical. Neither is Judaism
13 perpetrate terrorism are enemies of Muslims and Islam itself. Pakistan is the largest troop contributor
14 a result, suicide attacks became associated with Islam. No one pointed out that before 9/11, the
15 there is no such thing as radical Islam. One of the reasons that Islam was
16 religions all around the world. Terrorism negates Islam's humanistic outlook and noble values. Those
17 se certain Western leaders equated terrorism with Islam, talking of Islamic terrorism and radical Islam.
18 is radical Islam? There is only one Islam, the Islam we follow of the Prophet
19 there was no such thing as radical Islam. There are radicals, moderates and liberals in

Figure 2: Concordance of Islam's Positive Image by Pakistan

Themes Identified in Pakistan's UN speeches portraying Positive Image of Islam:

Islam protects minorities' rights (2 occurrences)

Islam is not a radical religion (5 occurrences)

Islam preaches tolerance (1 occurrence)

Islam provides assistance to its citizens (1 occurrence)

Islam is a religion of love, peace and compassion (1 occurrence)

1	to do with any religion. The terms "Islamic terrorism" and "Islamic radicalism", which are used
2	"Islamic terrorism". The moment the catchphrase "Islamic terrorism" is used, the whole world turns
3	is happening in Kashmir because the phrase "Islamic terrorism" keeps being used. That is what
4	message do the terms "radical Islam" and "Islamic terrorism" send to people in the West,
5	State and to invoke the mantra of "Islamic terrorism". The moment the catchphrase "Islamic terrorism"

Figure 3: Concordance of World's Perception regarding Islam by Pakistan

Themes Identified:

According to the world, Islam is a religion of terrorism (5 occurrences)

World perceives Islam as "radical Islam" (2 occurrences)

Table 4: Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Acts Used by Pakistan's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Speech Acts	Frequency	Percentage
Representatives	10	41.667%
Declaratives	2	8.334%
Commissives	1	4.167%
Expressives	8	33.334%
Directives	3	12.501%
Total	24	100%

Table 5: Frequencies and Percentages of Ethos, Logos and Pathos Used by Pakistan's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Rhetorical Appeals	Frequency	Percentage
Ethos	3	14.286%
Logos	14	66.667%
Pathos	4	19.048%
Total	21	100%

Table 6: Frequencies and Percentages of Other Figures of Speech Used by Pakistan's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Figures of Speech	Frequency	Percentage
Metaphor	1	5.882%
Overstatement	15	88.235%
Understatement	1	5.882%

Figures of Speech	Frequency	Percentage
Total	17	100%

4.3 Turkey

Table 7: Representation of Islamophobia by Turkey

Sr. No.	Sentences	Speaker	Year
1	We are resolved to actively pursue this objective and to work diligently with like-minded nations and international organizations to ensure that we take a united and effective stance against Islamophobia and all forms of hate.	Ahmet Davutoğlu	2012
2	Racism, xenophobia, Islamophobia and hate speech have reached an alarming level.	Recep Tayyip Erdoğan	2020
3	Turkey is also strongly against every kind of anti-Semitism, Islamophobia and racism.	Recep Tayyip Erdoğan	2014
4	Unfortunately, Islamophobia has become a new form of racism.	Ahmet Davutoğlu	2012
5	Unfortunately, Islamophobia has become a new form of racism.	Abdullah Gül	2013
6	Similarly, the whole world should accept that Islamophobia is also a crime against humanity.	Recep Tayyip Erdoğan	2014
7	Islamophobia is an alternate name for racism and discrimination.	Recep Tayyip Erdoğan	2016
8	The purpose of Islamophobia is clear and simple; it aims to create an abstract and imaginary enemy out of the millions of peace-loving Muslims all over the world.	Ahmet Davutoğlu	2012
9	In terms of racism, xenophobia and Islamophobia, we strive to prevent negativity from emerging in various parts of the world, especially in Europe.	Recep Tayyip Erdoğan	2018
10	We must act together against all forms of racism and xenophobia, including Islamophobia, without exception, only then can we collectively fight against extremism, radicalization and terrorism in an effective manner.	Ahmet Davutoğlu	2015

1 eace, to terrorism. It is highly offensive that Islam and terror are spoken of together. Similarly, tho
 2 /y underlining that the recent attacks against Islam and the Prophet Muhammad — peace be upon him —
 3 t Muhammad — peace be upon him — and Islam are outright provocations. They aim to pit nation
 4 to hatred can darken the bright face of Islam. At the same time, we condemn all the
 5 an acts Islamic are offending the religion of Islam, every other religion, and humankind generally. Tu
 6 betrayal against the soul, spirit and letter of Islam. However, the recent events are testament to a
 7 s xenophobia, racism and animosity against Islam, if the countries in the crisis-ridden regions
 8 . It is a city that is sacred to Islam, Judaism and Christianity, and should be treated
 9 npts to denigrate the most sacred values of Islam or any other faith. We condemn any type
 10 ophia, cultural racism and animosity against Islam. The most effective way of reversing this negativ
 11 to all religions. We strongly condemn tying Islam, which means peace, to terrorism. It is highly

Figure 4: Concordance of Islam's Positive Image by Turkey

Themes Identified:

Islam is a radiant religion

Islam is a religion of peace

1 eace, to terrorism. It is highly offensive that Islam and terror are spoken of together. Similarly, tho
 2 /y underlining that the recent attacks against Islam and the Prophet Muhammad — peace be upon him —
 3 t Muhammad — peace be upon him — and Islam are outright provocations. They aim to pit nation

Figure 5: Concordance of World's Perception regarding Islam by Turkey

Theme Identified:

World equates Islam with terrorism (1 occurrence)

Table 8: Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Acts Used by Turkey's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Speech Acts	Frequency	Percentage
Representatives	5	45.455%
Declaratives	1	9.091%
Commissives	0	0%
Expressives	4	36.364%
Directives	1	9.091%
Total	11	100%

Table 9: Frequencies and Percentages of Ethos, Logos and Pathos Used by Turkey's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Rhetorical Appeals	Frequency	Percentage
Ethos	2	15.385%
Logos	8	61.539%
Pathos	3	23.077%
Total	13	100%

Table 10: Frequencies and Percentages of Other Figures of Speech Used by Turkey's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Figures of Speech	Frequency	Percentage
Metaphor	0	0%
Overstatement	8	100%
Understatement	0	0%
Total	8	100%

4.4 Afghanistan

Table 11: Representation of Islamophobia by Afghanistan

Sr. No.	Sentences	Speaker	Year
1	I call on leaders in the West, both among politicians and in the media, to confront Islamophobia in all its many forms and manifestations; it is incumbent on us all to advance the cause of dialogue and cooperation, to fight the forces of division and hatred and to fulfill the promise of a better and brighter future for future generations.	Hâmid Karzai	2012
2	In particular, the menace of Islamophobia is a worrying phenomenon that threatens peace and coexistence among cultures and civilizations.	Hâmid Karzai	2012

1	in the holy verses of the Quran? Islam also considers the killing of one innocent
2	to further elucidate the true image of Islam and declare their condemnation of terrorists and
3	istence and present a moderate interpretation of Islam. In this regard, we welcome the express
4	agenda in Afghanistan. I would add that Islam is a religion with a clear thought,
5	humane religion, and are in fact using Islam only as a tool to achieve their
6	to achieve their evil goals. How can Islam possibly permit terrorism and suicide attacks, or
7	violence and cruelty under the guise of Islam. With their backward views, violence and brutal

Figure 6: Concordance of Islam's Positive Image by Afghanistan

Themes Identified:

Islam denounces the killings of human

Islam respects human values

Islam has nothing to do with terrorism

Table 12: Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Acts Used by Afghanistan's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Speech Acts	Frequency	Percentage
Representatives	0	0%
Declaratives	0	0%
Commissives	0	0%
Expressives	2	66.667%

Speech Acts	Frequency	Percentage
Directives	1	33.334%
Total	3	100%

Table 13: Frequencies and Percentages of Ethos, Logos and Pathos Used by Afghanistan's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Rhetorical Appeals	Frequency	Percentage
Ethos	1	33.334%
Logos	1	33.334%
Pathos	1	33.334%
Total	3	100%

Table 14: Frequencies and Percentages of Other Figures of Speech Used by Afghanistan's Muslim Leaders at UN Speeches

Figures of Speech	Frequency	Percentage
Metaphor	0	0%
Overstatement	2	100%
Understatement	0	0%
Total	2	100%

5. DISCUSSION

After 9/11, Islam has been associated with terrorism and hatred toward Islam has increased rapidly. Corpus analysis of 3 Muslim countries' speeches was conducted to find out the pragma-rhetorical strategies used to counter Islamophobia. These countries explicitly address the issue of Islamophobia. Muslim leaders defended Islam with their anti-Islamophobic speeches as shown in Table 2.

First Research Question: dealt with the speech acts. Analysis of data in terms of speech acts reveals how Muslim leaders use different types of speech acts in their UN speeches to discuss Islamophobia. The representative speech act is most frequently used by Muslim countries such as Pakistan (see Table 4.4) and Turkey (see Table 4.8). Representative speech acts come in the form of utterances referring to what the speaker believes is true (Christison, 2018). By using representative speech acts, Muslim speakers persuade audiences that there is no "radical Islam" in the world.

Number of representatives and expressives SA are equally used by the Muslim leaders at UN. Expressives speech act is used by countries like Afghanistan (see Table 4.12). The use of expressive SA delineates the painful psychological state of speakers because the world regards the presence of Islam as a threat. While representatives and expressives are used more dominantly by the speakers to make their speeches more informative, revealing the truth and convincing the audience by portraying a positive image of Islam, commissives and declaratives are the least used by Muslim leaders.

Second Research Question: dealt with the ways rhetorical appeals are used. To answer the second question, ethos, logos and pathos were investigated. The rhetorical appeals used most frequently by the

Muslim countries at UN are logos such as Pakistan (See Table 4.5), Turkey (See Table 4.9) and Afghanistan (See Table 4.13). Speakers have used logos the most to portray the truth that Islam has nothing to do with terrorism and provides logical arguments about the unkind consequences of Islamophobia. Akinwotu (2016) elucidates that "logos lies in the power of the speaker to provide truth by appealing to the sense of reason of the audience in persuasive argument" (p. 48).

The second most frequent strategy used by Muslim leaders in their UN speeches is pathos, in countries such as Afghanistan (see Table 4.13). Pathos is used to evoke audiences' emotions for persuasion. Akinwotu (2016) states that "the emotional disposition of the audience is very germane to the success of a speaker's persuasive efforts" (p. 47). The third RA used by speakers is ethos (to show reliability) by Muslim leaders like Afghanistan (see Table 4.13).

Third Research Question: is dealt with figures of speech. The analysis depicts that overstatement is commonly used in almost all Muslim leaders' UN speeches. The purpose of overstatement by the leaders is to concentrate on the role of peace among civilizations and to diminish the negative image of Islam and Muslims by portraying a positive image. Muslim leaders try to persuade the audiences to collectively eradicate Islamophobia globally.

6. CONCLUSION

The current study analyzed the corpus of Islamophobia consisting of English speeches delivered at the UNGA from 2012-2021. This research carried out a pragma-rhetorical analysis of Muslim leaders' UN speeches. Pragma-rhetorical analysis comprises two stages: pragmatic strategies (including speech acts) and rhetorical strategies (ethos, logos, pathos and other figures of speech). From data analysis, it can be inferred that Muslim countries frequently use "representatives" and "expressive" SAs in their speeches to combat Islamophobia and provide factual information regarding this issue. The rhetorical strategy "logos" is most dominantly used by the Muslim leaders to provide evidence and prove the facts of Islamophobia through logical argument to persuade the audience. Lastly, "overstatement" as a figure of speech is used by the Muslim leaders to emphasize the issue of Islamophobia and concentrate on the positive image of Islam and Muslims in their UN speeches. The analysis of the corpus for the current study reveals that Pakistan is at the top in addressing the issue of Islamophobia. Pakistan portrays a positive image of Islam and Muslims by countering Islamophobia. Secondly, Turkey also addresses the issue of Islamophobia and constructs a positive image of Islam. The third Muslim country that addresses this issue is Afghanistan which tries to diminish the negative image of Islam in the world. These countries use different strategies to eradicate the negative image of Islam as a radical religion of terrorists by addressing this issue positively.

Recommendations for Future Research

For future researchers, a comparative study of Muslim countries and Western countries regarding Islamophobia can be conducted. Additionally, research could explore the effectiveness of these pragma-rhetorical strategies on Western audiences or examine how the framing of Islamophobia has evolved in UN speeches over time.

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